

Factors Affecting the Intention to Choose Cultural Travel Destinations Associated with Experience of Domestic Tourists: Research at the Lotus Silk Village Phung Xa, Ha Noi

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Abstract:

Culture-based travel associated with experiential activities is becoming increasingly popular and favored by domestic tourists in Vietnam. In that context, understanding the factors influencing tourists' intentions of choosing destinations is paramount. The lotus silk village Phung Xa, Ha Noi, with cultural values and unique experiences, is a typical example of such cultural travel destinations. This study utilizes the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), factors incorporated into the model include Travel Motivation (TM), Destination Information (DI), Attitude (AT), Subjective Norm (SN), and Perceived Behavioral Control (PBC), which impact the dependent variable "Intention of choosing cultural tourism

destinations involved with experiential activities at the Phung Xa lotus silk village Hanoi" (IC). The results show that Attitude (AT) has the strongest influence on the intention to choose Phung Xa lotus silk village as an experiential cultural tourism destination, with an impact level of 0.332; Perceived Behavioral Control (PBC) has an impact level of 0.207; and Travel Motivation (TM) has an impact level of 0.195. The factors Destination Information (DI) and Subjective Norm (SN) are not statistically significant to conclude their influence on the dependent variable 'Intention to choose Phung Xa lotus silk village as an experiential cultural tourism destination' (IC).

Keywords: *Domestic tourists, intention, destinations, cultural tourism associated with experience, lotus silk weaving, Phung Xa - Ha Noi.*

Introduction

Cultural tourism is an important form of traveling that attracts the interest of many travelers around the world. The difference between cultural tourism associated with experience and regular cultural tourism lies in the approach, the motivations of the tourists, and the methods of engaging in activities at the destination. Cultural tourism associated with

experiential activities has been becoming increasingly popular in recent years. Tourists are progressively interested in exploring new sites and experiencing unique cultures. This type of tourism is expected to continue growing in the future, contributing in boosting the development of cultural tourism and preservation of local cultures.

Hanoi is implementing the “Discover the Nam Thang Long Heritage Route” tourism project, which includes two itineraries: Hanoi Center - Thanh Tri - Thuong Tin - Phu Xuyen and Hanoi Center - Thanh Oai - Ung Hoa - My Duc. Lotus silk weaving workshop in Phung Xa craft village is one of the stops along this heritage route. Recently selected by the Hanoi Department of Tourism as one of the destinations in the 'Discover the Nam Thang Long Heritage Route' tour that connects the city center with suburban areas, Phung Xa craft village promises to be an attractive destination for many travelers who want to learn about, explore, and experience the lotus silk weaving process.

Although located more than 40 kilometers away from the center of Hanoi, in recent times, many tourists have come to visit and experience the process of producing lotus silk in Phung Xa village. Not only being a sacred and noble symbol, lotus is also particularly familiar to every Vietnamese person. Apart from its role as food, used to create delicious and nutritious dishes, lotus plants can also be turned into unique and sophisticated products by the hands of artisans. Lotus silk is a soft, light fabric woven from the silk fibers taken from the stems of lotus flowers. This is one of the fabrics with a complex production process, requiring a lot of effort, and is among the most expensive in the world (sendaiviet.com, 2022). The peak period for lotus silk production in Phung Xa is only from May to September each year. This is also the time when Phung Xa artisans focus on producing lotus silk, creating artistic works for decoration, display, and as souvenirs.

Currently, research on cultural tourism linked with experiences primarily focuses on analyzing internal issues, with very few studies coming from the perspective of tourists. The aims of this research are to contribute to the development of theoretical understanding regarding behavioral intentions in choosing cultural tourism destinations associated with experiences; Seek to identify the key factors affecting the intention to choose cultural tourism destinations linked with experiences, specifically studied at Phung Xa lotus silk village in Hanoi. Based on this, tourism managers, travel companies, and related entities

can better understand the needs, motivations, and expectations of tourists when choosing cultural tourism experiences at Phung Xa lotus silk village in Hanoi, thereby developing more effective tourism management strategies and policies.

Theoretical Basis

Some Concepts

(i) Cultural tourism associated with experience

The Vietnam Tourism Law 2017 defined tourism as follows:

“Tourism refers to activities related to a person’s journey outside of their usual place of residence for no more than 01 year continuously, with the purpose of meeting the needs for sightseeing, relaxation, entertainment, exploration, discovering tourism resources, or combined with other legal purposes.” (National Assembly, 2017).

Overtime, the concept of tourism has been supplemented and refined in its scope. However, the content of this concept can be summarized through 03 basic factors: (1) Tourism involves temporary travel over a certain period; (2) Tourism is a journey to a destination, using services such as accommodation, dining, etc. and participating in activities in order to meet the needs of tourists at the destinations; (3) The trip may have multiple specific or combined purposes, excluding the intent of settling or working at the destination.

According to the United Nations World Tourism Organization (UNWTO), cultural tourism is a type of tourism activity, in which the main motivation of tourists is to learn, discovering, experience and consume products at the destination. These attraction sites are related to the material, intellectual, spiritual, and emotional characteristics of a society, including arts and architecture, historical and cultural heritage, cuisine, literature, music, creative industries and living cultures with their lifestyles, value systems, beliefs, and traditions.

In Vietnam,

“Cultural tourism is a tourism form developed based on exploiting cultural values, contributing in the preservation and promotion of traditional cultural values, and honoring new cultural values of humankind.” (National Assembly, 2017).

Experience-based tourism is a form of tourism that provides travelers with the opportunity to engage in real-life experiences in new living environments. Participating in experience-based tourism involves immersing oneself in the real-life environment of tourist destinations by learning about information and engaging in specific activities as direct members of the local environment and community. These activities can provide tourists with more interesting experiences of life in new environments that are different from their everyday lives, while also gaining additional knowledge and practical experience about nature, culture, and society. In Vietnam, cultural tourism is one of the tourism products within the group of tourism development policies encouraged and supported by the government.

Cultural tourism resources include historical and cultural relics, revolutionary sites, archeology, architecture; traditional cultural values, festivals,

folk performing arts and other cultural values; creative works of human labor may also be used for tourism purposes (National Assembly, 2017). These also serve as resources for developing cultural tourism associated with experience.

Based on individual perspectives of culture-based tourism and experience-based tourism, this paper approaches the definition:

“Cultural tourism associated with experience is a form of tourism activity in which the main motivation of the tourists is to learn, discover, engage in specific activities linked with cultural characteristics of the destination, including: arts, architecture, historic and cultural heritage, cuisine, literature, music, writing, and living cultures with their lifestyles, value systems, and traditions”.

Tourists participating in cultural tourism associated with experience will play the role of direct members of the local environment and community, gaining more interesting experiences of life in new environments that are different from their everyday lives, while also accumulating additional knowledge and practical experience about nature, culture, and society. The differences between cultural tourism and cultural tourism associated with experience is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Distinguishing between Cultural Tourism and Cultural Tourism Associated with Experience

Criteria	Cultural tourism	Cultural tourism associated with experience
Tourist motivations and objectives	Explore and learn about the culture, history, and art of a destination	To emphasize the direct involvement of tourists in cultural activities at the destination
Tourist participation	Observation	Not only observing but also actively engaging in the daily activities of the local community and living life as a member of that community
Values provided	Providing tourists with a deeper knowledge of the local culture, history, and art	Offering greater value in terms of individual experience. Tourists not only learn new knowledge but also accumulate hands-on experiences, new skills and create memorable moments with the local community

Both forms of tourism offer unique values, depending on individual preferences and goals. However, cultural tourism associated with experience is becoming increasingly popular due to its ability to provide deeper, more authentic, and meaningful experiences for travellers.

Experiential cultural tourism focuses on creating genuine and profound experiences for tourists regarding local culture. This form of travel encourages direct interactions with the natives, engagement in traditional cultural activities and

exploration of the unique aspects of local culture.

The characteristics of experiential cultural tourism are:

- **Interaction:** Cultural tourism with experiential elements emphasizes interactions between tourists and natives. Travelers are not only observers but also active participants in cultural activities, learning new skills, and experiencing the local way of life.
- **Authenticity:** This form of tourism aims to provide travelers with the most authentic and original cultural experiences. Tourists are able to access local culture directly and naturally, without any arrangements or staging.
- **Personalization:** Cultural tourism associated with experience is tailored to cater for individual needs and preferences of each traveler. Tourists can opt for participating in activities suitable for their interests and needs.
- **Sustainability:** This type of tourism aims towards the sustainable development and preservation of local culture. Travelers are encouraged to use local travel services, purchase handicrafts, and respect the local cultural environment.

(ii) Travel destination

Tourism is a specific activity, with a spatial destination. The United Nations World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) defines a tourism destination as follows:

“A tourism destination is a geographical space where tourists stay at least one night, have tourism products, providing services, tourism resources that attract visitors, administrative boundaries for management, and a recognizable image to determine competitiveness in the market.” (UNWTO,2005)

Traditionally, a tourism destination is simply defined by its geographical elements and territorial scope. Under this perspective, a destination refers to a place that attracts tourists due to its diverse resources, quality, and a range of amenities and services offered to visitors (Davison & Maitland, 2000). From a business perspective, a tourism destination is considered

as a product or a brand, (Mike & Caster, 2007) argue that a tourism destination is a combination of six elements to attract tourists: attractions, facilities, accessibility, human resources, image and distinctiveness, and price." As this paper researched the intention to choose cultural destinations of tourists, the authors opted for Mike & Caster, (2007)'s approach.

(iii) Domestic tourists

- According to the United Nations World Tourism Organization (UNWTO), domestic tourists are those who travel within their country of residence without crossing international borders. They can participate in various types of tourism such as leisure tourism, ecotourism, cultural tourism, religious tourism, and many others. Domestic tourism is not limited to visiting landmarks but also includes exploring, learning, and experiencing in different regions of the country.
- According to Vietnam's Tourism Law (National Assembly, 2017), *“A tourist is a person who travels or combines travel, except for cases of studying, working for income at the destination”*. Vietnam classifies **tourists into three categories:** (1) **Domestic tourists are** Vietnamese citizens or foreigners residing in Vietnam travel within Vietnam territory; (2) **International inbound tourists are** foreigners or overseas Vietnamese who travel to Vietnam; (3) **Outbound tourists are** Vietnamese citizens and foreigners residing in Vietnam who travel abroad. Within the scope of this article, the authors only study the behavior of choosing travel destinations of domestic tourists.
- Different from international tourism, domestic tourism usually has a shorter period, lasting from a few days to a week. In recent years, domestic tourism has witnessed a rapid growth (Vietnam National Administration of Tourism, 2022), partly because of the development of the transportation infrastructure, government tourism incentives, and a shift in public perception of the value of domestic tourism. Domestic tourists tend to choose destinations closer to home or popular domestic landmarks. In the development trend of experiential cultural tourism, eco-tourism areas, historical sites, and

traditional craft villages also attract a large number of domestic tourists. Accommodation, food and beverage, and entertainment are popular spending categories for domestic tourists. According to a study by Đinh., N.V., (2020), domestic tourists in Vietnam often prefer high-value added tourism products, for example, tours combining cultural experiences, local cuisine, craft villages exploration, visits to traditional festivals, and participation in agricultural production activities.

General Research about the Intention to Choose Cultural Travel Destinations Associated with Experience

The Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), developed by Ajzen (1991), is one of the most widely used models for predicting and explaining human behavior. TPB consists of three main components: attitude toward the behavior, subjective norm, and perceived behavioral control.

(i) Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) model, Basic factors in this theory (independent variables)

Attitude toward the behavior: is an individual's evaluation of the outcomes that will result from performing a specific behavior. Attitude toward the behavior is an individual's positive or negative feelings about performing a specific behavior. This attitude is formed from personal beliefs about the consequences of the behavior and the individual's evaluation of these consequences.

Subjective norm: is the individual's perception of social pressure or the expectations of others regarding whether to perform a behavior or not. Subjective norm is formed from beliefs about the expectations of important others and the individual's motivation to comply with these expectations.

Perceived behavioral control: is an individual's perception of the ease or difficulty of performing a specific behavior; this depends on the availability of resources and opportunities to perform the behavior.

Behavioral intention: is an indication of an individual's readiness to perform a specific

behavior. It is considered a prerequisite for performing the behavior; it is based on attitude towards the behavior, subjective norm, and perceived behavioral control.

In addition to the three main components of TPB, this study adds three more variables to further clarify the intention to choose cultural tourism destinations associated with the experiences of domestic tourists: travel motivation, destination information, and destination image.

(ii) Theory of Destination Choice

Travel motivation: refers to the reasons that drive individuals to engage in tourism activities. These motivations can include the need for rest, relaxation, exploration of new cultures, the acquisition of new knowledge, or seeking new experiences. The theoretical foundation for proposing the theoretical research model and hypothesis for this study are the general mode of travel motivation by Crompton (1979) and the model of factors affecting destination choice by Woodside, A. G., & Lysonski, S. (1989); Um, S., & Crompton, J. L. (1990), and Hill, T. H. (2000). According to Crompton (1979), travel motivations are divided into two main groups: push factors and pull factors. Push factors are internal factors such as the need for exploration, relaxation, and learning. Pull factors are external factors such as natural beauty, cultural heritage, and recreational activities at the destination. The research results of Lang., D.N.,(2024) also highlight that the motivation to learn and experience has the greatest impact on the choice of community-based tourism in the Central Highlands of Vietnam.

Destination information: is the quantity and quality of information that tourists receive about a specific destination (Chon, K. S., 1992). This information can include newspaper articles, reviews from previous tourists, images, videos, or information from tourism websites. Destination information can strongly influence the decision of tourists as it helps them visualize the future experiences and evaluate the attractiveness of that destination. Additionally, the attractiveness of a destination positively impacts on tourists' satisfaction and intention to

return. (Thuy., T.T., & Tuấn., L.A., 2018; Nhật., H.B., & Khanh., N.P., 2018)

(iii) Proposed research model

Based on the general research, the authors propose the research model for the topic: “Factors affecting the intention to choose cultural travel destinations associated with experience of domestic tourists - Research at the Lotus Silk Village Phung Xa - Hanoi”.

Figure 1. Proposed Framework for the Study

Source: Proposal of the research group

Research Hypotheses

- Hypothesis H1: Travel motivation has a positive relationship with the intention to choose cultural travel destinations associated with experience.
- Hypothesis H2: Destination information has a positive relationship with the intention to choose cultural travel destinations associated with experience.
- Hypothesis H3: Attitude has a positive relationship with the intention to choose cultural travel destinations associated with experience.
- Hypothesis H4: Subjective norm has a positive relationship with the intention to choose cultural travel destinations associated with experience.
- Hypothesis H5: Perceived behavioral control has a positive relationship with the intention to choose cultural travel destinations associated with experience.

Table 1. Basis for Constructing Variables and Factor Scales in the Model

Ordinal Numbers	Symbols	Scales	Sources
1	Attitude- AT: Domestic tourists' perceptions and assessments of the tourism experience at Phung Xa lotus silk weaving village.		
	AT1	I think Phung Xa lotus silk weaving village to have a visually appealing scenery.	Ajzen (1991), Lam & Hsu (2004)
	AT2	I think Phung Xa lotus silk weaving village is an accessible destination.	
	AT3	I think the experiential activities at Phung Xa lotus silk weaving village are interesting.	
	AT4	I think this village has a diverse cultural tradition.	
	AT5	I think this village has good infrastructure.	
	AT6	I think Phung Xa lotus silk weaving village is worth visiting.	
2	Subjective Norm- SN: Influences of relatives, friends, and the society on your travel decision		
	SN1	Relatives	Ajzen (1991), Han (2015)
	SN2	Friends	
	SN3	Media (Tiktok, Instagram, Facebook, Threads,...)	
3	Perceived Behavioral Control- PBC: Tourists' ability and confidence to travel		
	PBC1	I find it easy to travel and experience the culture at Phung Xa lotus silk weak village.	Ajzen (1991), Sparks (2007)
	PBC2	I have the ability to self- organize a trip to this craft village.	
	PBC3	I am financially capable of visiting this craft village.	
	PBC4	I can allocate time to experience cultural tourism during the peak lotus season in Phung Xa village.	

4	Travel Motivation- TM: Motivations and desires that drive tourists to choose a destination		
	TM1	I want to explore the culture at Phung Xa lotus silk weaving village.	Crompton (1979), Fodness (1994)
	TM2	I want to unwind and enjoy myself in this village.	
	TM3	I want to learn and broaden my knowledge when visiting this craft village.	
	TM4	I want to prove myself when visiting this craft village.	
5	Destination Information- DI: The availability and quality of destination information that tourists receive.		
	DI1	I usually research comprehensively about the destinations before traveling.	Bigné et al. (2001), Gursoy & McCleary (2004) Echtner, C. M., & Ritchie, J. R. (1991):
	DI2	I usually pay attention to the credibility of information (consistency across different sources) about travel destinations.	
	DI3	I can easily find information about this craft village.	
6	Intention of Choosing (IC)		
	IC1	I am considering choosing the Phung Xa lotus silk weaving village as my experiential travel destination in near future.	Ajzen, I., 1991
	IC2	There is a high probability that I will choose the Phung Xa lotus silk weaving village as my experiential travel destination.	
	IC3	I am certain that I will choose the Phung Xa lotus silk weaving village as my experiential travel destination.	

Source: The authors develop and propose

Research Methodology

Data Acquisition Methods

Based on the theoretical framework and literature review of the factors influencing destination choice, the factors included in the research model are: Travel motivation (TM); Destination information (DI); Attitude (AT); Subjective norm (SN); Perceived behavioral control (PBC). The dependent variable is "Intention of choosing cultural tourism destinations involved with experiential activities at the Phung Xa lotus silk village Hanoi" (IC).

The questionnaire was constructed using a 5-point Likert scale with the following scales:

1. *Strongly disagree*
2. *Disagree*
3. *Neutral*
4. *Agree*
5. *Strongly agree*

The quantitative research method was conducted to collect the opinions of domestic tourists living in Vietnam. After constructing the questionnaire, the research group conducted a pilot survey with 5 people who were frequent experiential travelers. The preliminary survey results showed that the opinions agreed with the factors included in the model.

Due to limitations in time and resources for the survey, the author used the convenience sampling method. The minimum sample size required to achieve reliability according to the formula is $n=50+8m$ (m : number of independent variables) (Tabachnick and Fidell, 1996). In the case of this research with 5 variables, the minimum number of questionnaires needed to collect is $50 + 85 = 90$ questionnaires. The survey respondents were residents of Hanoi. From the perspective of collecting as many samples as possible to ensure the stability of the impact, based on the ability to collect samples, the research group decided that the number of questionnaires to be issued should be $n > 150$. The questionnaires were sent to respondents online via a link (<https://forms.gle/JNyMYmkRgBwqEbFe6>). The number of questionnaires returned was 155, which were included in the analysis of influencing factors.

Data Processing Methods

The quantitative research method was conducted to process the research data collected from the survey of Hanoi residents. The structural regression equation has the general form:

The quantitative research method was conducted to process the research data collected from the survey of Hanoi residents. The structural regression equation has the general form:

$$IC = a + TM + b * DI + c * AT + d * SN + e * PBC \quad (1)$$

The SMARTPLS software was used to test the hypotheses and evaluate the impact of the factors.

Step 1: Evaluate the measurement model

The measurement model is evaluated by considering the contribution of observed variables (outer loadings), the reliability of the scale (Cronbach's Alpha), convergence (Convergence), and discriminant validity (Discriminant Validity).

Step 2: Evaluate the structural model

When the measurement model meets the requirements, proceed to evaluate the structural model through the impact relationship, path coefficient, overall determination coefficient R square, effect size coefficient f square.

In addition, to assess the impact of each factor, the group conducted the determination of the range value and the average value of each factor, and determined the average score range in which the answer falls.

$$\text{Range value} = (\text{Maximum} - \text{Minimum}) / n(5-1) / 5-0.8$$

Evaluation thresholds based on average score:

- 1.00 – 1.80: Strongly disagree
- 1.81 – 2.60: Disagree
- 2.61-3.40: Neutral
- 3.41 – 4.20: Agree
- 4.21 – 5.00: Strongly agree

Research Results

General Information about Lotus Silk Weaving Village Phung Xa – Ha Noi

Phung Xa village is located in My Duc district, Hanoi (about 40 kilometers from Hanoi City Center). Currently, this destination is in the new tourism route: “Discover the Nam Thang Long Heritage Route”, which was launched by Hanoi Department of Tourism in April 2024. Phung Xa village is famous for its lotus silk weaving craft. Phung Xa lotus silk products are not only beautiful but also carry significant cultural and historical values. Visitors coming here can not only admire the delicate silk weaving process but also have the opportunity to participate in the production activities and learn about the history and culture of the village. If the tourists come to the village during the lotus season from May to September, they can experience the process of spinning silk threads, making silk, weaving silk, and even trying their hands at creating unique silk products (sendaiviet.com, 2022). This is also the most favorable time for the development of cultural tourism combined with experiential activities.

Lotus silk was researched and developed by artisan Phan Thi Thuan and was recognized in 2017. She is also a tour guide, introducing Phung Xa weaving village, the process of growing mulberry trees, raising silkworms, and growing lotus to make lotus silk to the visitors. The process of making lotus silk requires artisans to be very skillful, meticulous, and follow strict procedures and techniques to obtain high-quality silk threads. A seasonal and skilled artisan can only extract lotus silk from 200 – 250 lotus petioles in a day (sendaiviet.com, 2022). Each lotus stem will produce a silk thread about 100 centimeters long. Notably, all lotus petioles must be processed within 24 hours, otherwise they will dry out, the silk will retract, and the thread will completely be spoiled. After separating and cleaning the silk, Phung Xa artisans put the silk into spinning wheels to create skeins and then dry them. Unlike industrial production processes, handmade lotus silk products often have unique and non-uniform characteristics. The production process, from harvesting lotus petioles to weaving and completing products, requires the skill and patience of artisans. Firstly, harvesting lotus stems requires intense concentration and sophisticated technique. Each

lotus stem needs to be carefully selected and harvested to ensure the quality of the silk thread later. As a result, this means an increase in labor costs and time. Next, the process of weaving lotus silk is also a complex and costly one. Artisans must carefully and meticulously perform all stages of the manual weaving process, from stretching threads, weaving silk to completing the final product.

From lotus silk, artisans in Phung Xa village create a variety of products such as silk scarves, bags, notebook covers, home decorations, and souvenirs. These products have significant commercial value and are popular in upscale establishments like hotels, spas, and resorts. Lotus silk being cool and comfortable, with excellent elasticity, creates a pleasant feeling

against skin. Its smooth and glossy surface also contributes to the products' high aesthetic and quality standards. All these qualities make the lotus silk products unique and luxurious, increasing their values and attracting customers. Currently, the village's products are not only popular among domestic customers but are also exported to demanding markets such as Japan, Germany, Belgium, China, and Saudi Arabia. In 2019, lotus silk products were honored to be chosen by the Prime Minister as Vietnam's gifts at the G20 Summit in Japan.

Descriptions of Survey Participants

The survey link has received a total of 155 responses. The collected data provides demographic information such as gender, occupation, and age:

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics of Survey Participants

Occupations	Number of People	Percentage (%)
Students	71	45,8 %
College students	34	21,9 %
Employees	45	29%
Retired	5	3,2%
Gender		
Male	60	38,7%
Female	93	60%
Prefer not to say	2	1,3%
Age		
Under 18	75	48,4%
19-29	31	20%
30-40	20	12,9%
41-60	24	15,5%
Over 60	5	3,2%

Source: Survey results

The majority of survey participants were students, accounting for 71 individuals or 45.8% of the total. Other occupations included 34 students (21.9%), 45 employees (29%), and 5 retirees (3.2%).

Most participants were under 18 years old, with 75 individuals (48.4%). The age groups of 19-29, 30-40, 41-60, and over 60 accounted for 20%,

12.9%, 15.5%, and 3.2% of the participants, respectively.

Regarding gender, the survey primarily involved females (93 individuals, 60%), followed by males (60 individuals, 38.7%). A small percentage of 2 individuals (1.3%) preferred not to disclose their gender.

Results of Model Testing

Results of the Assessment of the Quality of Observed Variables in the Measurement Model

The research group conducted a model run, and the quality of observed variables was evaluated through outer loadings. The quality of the observed variables is shown in Table 3.

Table 3. The Outer Loadings of the Factors that Influence Intention of Choosing Cultural Tourism Destinations Involved with Experiential Activities at the Phung Xa Lotus Silk Village Hanoi

	AT	DI	IC	PBC	SN	TM
AT2	0,774					
AT3	0,797					
AT5	0,831					
AT6	0,794					
DI1		0,808				
DI2		0,726				
DI3		0,814				
IC1			0,888			
IC2			0,906			
IC3			0,896			
PBC1				0,793		
PBC2				0,829		
PBC3				0,823		
PBC4				0,823		
SN2					1,000	
TM1						0,903
TM2						0,816
TM3						0,803
AT1	0,834					

Source: Evaluation results from the research group

The results from Table 3 show that the outer loadings of all correlation coefficients of the total variables affecting the intention of choosing Phung Xa lotus silk village as a cultural experience tourism destination (all > 0.7) (Hair et al., 2016) indicate that the observed variables are significant.

Reliability assessment of the scale

Evaluate the scale's reliability of the factors that influence intention of choosing cultural tourism destinations involved with experiential activities at the Phung Xa lotus silk village on PLS-SEM through two primary indices: Cronbach's Alpha và Composite Reliability (CR).

Table 4. Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability of the Factors that Influence Intention of Choosing Cultural Tourism Destinations Involved with Experiential Activities at the Phung Xa Lotus Silk Village

	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
AT	0,866	0,869	0,903	0,650
DI	0,709	0,752	0,827	0,615
IC	0,878	0,880	0,925	0,804
PBC	0,835	0,840	0,889	0,667
SN	1,000	1,000	1,000	1,000
TM	0,795	0,818	0,879	0,709

Source: Evaluation results from the research group

According to Table 4, after the reliability test using Cronbach's Alpha coefficient, the results showed that: Attitude (AT) reached 0.866; Destination information (DI) reached 0.709; Perceived behavioral control (PBC) reached 0.835; Subjective norm (SN) reached 1.000; Travel motivation TM reached 0.795; 'Intention to choose Phuong Xa lotus silk village as a cultural experience tourism destination' (IC) reached 0.878. Thus, all scales meet the criterion > 0.7 (DeVellis, 2012) and do not violate any rules for variable elimination, so no variables were eliminated and they can be accepted in terms of reliability

Composite Reliability (CR) of all the observed variables are > 0.7 (Bagozzi & Yi, 1988) (Table 4). Therefore, the scale has reliability, has analytical validity, and is used in subsequent factor analysis.

Convergence

According to statistical analysis in Table 4, the average variance extracted (AVE) of each factor is as follows: Attitude (AT) is 0.650; Destination

information (DI) is 0.615; Perceived behavioral control (PBC) is 0.667; Subjective norm (SN) is 1.000; Travel motivation (TM) is 0.709; and 'Intention to choose Phuong Xa lotus silk village as a cultural experience tourism destination' (IC) is 0.804. Thus, the average variance extracted (AVE) of all variables is greater than 0.5 (Hock & Ringle, 2010), indicating that the model meets the convergence validity criteria.

Discriminant Validity

As shown in Table 5, the Fornell-Larcker criterion for the model examining the factors influencing: Attitude (AT), Destination information (DI), Perceived behavioral control (PBC), Subjective norm (SN), Travel motivation (TM), and 'Intention to choose Phuong Xa lotus silk village as a cultural experience tourism destination' (IC) ensures discriminant validity, as all the square root values of AVE on the diagonal are higher than the off-diagonal values. Therefore, in terms of discriminant validity, both the cross-loading factor and the Fornell-Larcker criterion are met.

Table 5. The Fornell-Larcker Criterion for the Model Examining the Factors Influencing Intention to Choose Phuong Xa Lotus Silk Village as a Cultural Experience Tourism Destination

	AT	DI	IC	PBC	SN	TM
AT	0,806					

DI	0,555	0,784				
IC	0,676	0,514	0,897			
PBC	0,634	0,619	0,608	0,817		
SN	0,430	0,428	0,425	0,417	1,000	
TM	0,746	0,584	0,639	0,626	0,416	0,842

Source: Evaluation results from the research group

The function f^2 value

The function f^2 value indicates the magnitude of the influence of a structure (factor) when it is excluded from the model. The values of f^2

corresponding to 0.02, 0.15, and 0.35 represent small, medium, and large effect (Cohen, 1988), of the exogenous variable. If the effect size < 0.02 , it is considered to have no effect.

Table 6. Summary table of f^2 values

	AT	DI	IC	PBC	SN	TM
AT			0,332			
DI			0,047			
IC						
PBC			0,207			
SN			0,095			
TM			0,195			

Source: Evaluation results from the research group

In this model, Table 6 shows that the factors, include: Attitude (AT) is 0.332; Destination information (DI) is 0.047; Perceived behavioral control (PBC) is 0.207; Subjective norm (SN) is 0.095; Travel motivation (TM) is 0.195; which have a moderate influence on the 'Intention to choose Phung Xa lotus silk village as a cultural experience tourism destination' (IC).

Results of the Assessment of the Impact Level Using Structural Equation Modeling

Assessment of the correlation

The relationships and the influences of the factors that affect the intention to choose Phung Xa lotus silk village as a cultural experience tourism destination on SMARTPLS is presented in Figure 2.

The results of the Bootstrap analysis to assess the influence relationships are shown in Table 7.

Accordingly, the variables: Attitude (AT); Perceived behavioral control (PBC); Travel motivation (TM) have influences on the 'Intention to choose Phung Xa lotus silk village as a cultural travel destination associated with experiential activities' (IC) with P values < 0.05 ; this reflects these factors are statistically significant to show positive relationships with the 'Intention to choose Phung Xa lotus silk village as a cultural travel destination associated with experiential activities' (Hypotheses H1, H3, H5 are accepted). The variables Destination information (DI) and Subjective norm (SN) have P values > 0.1 ; this reflects these factors are not statistically significant to show relationships with 'Intention to choose Phung Xa lotus silk village as a cultural travel destination associated with experiential activities' (Hypotheses H2 and H4 are not accepted).

Figure 2. Factors that Impact the Intention to Choose Phung Xa Lotus Silk Village as a Cultural Experience Tourism Destination

Source: SMARTPLS analysis results of the research team

Table 7. Path Coefficient of the Structural Model

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
AT -> IC	0,332	0,339	0,084	3,943	0,000
DI -> IC	0,047	0,068	0,088	0,538	0,591
PBC -> IC	0,207	0,208	0,104	1,979	0,048
SN -> IC	0,095	0,084	0,080	1,195	0,233
TM -> IC	0,195	0,182	0,099	1,961	0,050

Source: SMARTPLS analysis results of the research team

The results of the testing in Table 7 show that with a confidence level of 90%, Attitude (AT) has the strongest influence on the 'Intention to choose Phung Xa lotus silk village as a cultural experience tourism destination' with an influence level of 0.332; Perceived behavioral control (PBC) has an influence level of 0.207; Travel motivation (TM) has an influence level of 0.195 on the 'Intention to choose Phung Xa lotus silk village as a cultural travel destination associated with experiential activities' (IC). The factors Destination information (DI) and Subjective norm (SN) are not statistically

significant to conclude their influence on the dependent variable 'Intention to choose Phung Xa lotus silk village as a cultural travel destination associated with experiential activities' (IC).

Therefore, we have the following structural regression equation:

$$IC = 0.332*AT + 0.207*PBC + 0.195*TM$$

Evaluation of the overall coefficient of determination R² (R square)

The PLS Algorithm analysis yields an R² value², reflecting the degree of explanation of the independent variables for the dependent variable. The R² index measures the overall coefficient of determination (R-square value), which is an indicator to measure the goodness of fit to the model of the data (the model's explanatory power). According to Hair et al. (2010), it is suggested that the R-square value should be at 0.75, 0.50, or 0.25.

Table 8. The Coefficient of Determination (R²) of Independent Variables for the Dependent Variable

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
IC	0,539	0,524

Source: Evaluation results from the research group

The results from Table 8 show that R² of 0.539 and R² Adjusted of 0.524, which is suitable for this research context. Thus, the independent variables in the model explain 53.9% of the "Intention to choose Phuong Xa lotus silk village as a cultural travel destination associated with experiential activities"

Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR)

Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR) index: This index indicates the goodness of fit of the research model. According to Hu & Bentler (1999), a well-fitting model typically has an SRMR value less than 0.08.

Table 9. Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR) index

	Saturated Model	Estimated Model
SRMR	0,078	0,078

Source: Evaluation results from the research group

Based on the results in Table 9, the SRMR of the research model is less than 0.08. Therefore, this model is suitable for data analysis.

Discussion

The research on "Factors affecting the intention to choose cultural tourism destinations associated with the experiences of domestic tourists" at Phung Xa lotus silk village showed that:

Attitude (AT) had the strongest influence on the Intention to Choose Destination (IC)

With a coefficient of influence of 0.332, meaning that when the attitude increases by 1 unit, the intention to choose cultural tourism destinations associated with experiences at Phung Xa lotus silk village increases by 0.332 units.

Figure 3. Mean Values of Observed Variables for the Attitude (AT) Factor

Source: Evaluation results from the research group

Among the attitude factors towards Phung Xa lotus silk weaving village, AT4 (rich cultural traditions) AT3 (interesting experiential activities), and AT6 (overall assessment as a worthwhile destination) were the 03 factors that receive the highest agreement from survey participants. This shows that domestic tourists pay attention to cultural elements and

experiential activities at the craft village. If they have a positive impression of the destination, they are more likely to choose Phung Xa lotus silk village as a cultural tourism destination. Enhancing positive experiences, perceptions, and images of the village could be a key strategy to attract visitors.

Perceived Behavior Control (PBC): PBC had a coefficient of influence of 0.207, showing that when tourists feel they can easily and conveniently visit the craft village, they are more likely to choose this destination. This factor could be related to the ease of access, costs, or other conditions.

Figure 4. The Average Scores of the Observed Variables of Perceived Behavior Control (PBC) Factor

Source: Evaluation results from the research group

Phung Xa village is located only 40 kilometers away from Hanoi, which is convenient to travel; therefore, PBC3 factor: “I am financially capable of visiting this craft village.” achieved the highest average score of 3.813 points, followed by PBC1: “I find it easy to travel and experience the culture at Phung Xa lotus silk weak village” and PBC4: “I can allocate time to experience cultural tourism during the peak lotus season in Phung Xa village” with 3.619 and 3.561 points, respectively. The lowest is PBC2: “I have the ability to self-organize a trip to this craft village” with 3.548 points.

Travel Motivation (TM): Understand travel motivation thoroughly is paramount in

developing and managing travel services effectively as it helps define the needs and expectations of tourists. Results of the survey about experiential cultural travel motivation at Phung Xa village are presented in Figure 5.

Figure 5. The Average Scores of the Observed Variables of Travel Motivation (TM) Factor

Source: Evaluation results from the research group

Among the factors that motivate domestic tourists to choose Phung Xa lotus silk village as a experiential cultural tourism destination, TM3 – wanting to learn and expand knowledge; TM1– wanting to explore culture, and TM2 – wanting to relax and entertain received the highest agreement from survey participants, with the average scores being 3.948; 3.884; and 3.652 points respectively. The least chosen motivation was self-expression (TM4), with a figure of 2.671 points. It shows that tourism motivations related to cultural discovery, experiences, and entertainment are highly valued by tourists.

The intention to choose Phung Xa lotus silk village as a tourism destination is divided into three levels “Intend to choose in the near future”; “Highly likely to choose”; and the highest level, “Definitely will choose”.

Figure 6. The Average Scores of the Observed Variables of “Intention of Choosing Phung Xa Lotus Silk Village Hanoi as a Cultural Tourism Destination Involved with Experiential Activities” Factor

Source: Evaluation results from the research group

The survey results in Figure 4 indicate that many respondents plan to visit the craft village in the near future. While this may suggest initial interest, it may not reflect a firm commitment. This presents an opportunity to attract future tourists, but additional incentives are required to convert intentions into visits.

The survey results show a decline in tourists' commitment to visiting the craft village, with lower average scores for "Highly likely to choose" (3.277) and "Definitely will choose" (2.871). It suggests that the number of people committed to choosing Phung Xa lotus silk village as a destination is not high. Therefore, potential barriers may include time constraints, cost, insufficient information, lack of unique experiences, or the appeal of other destinations.

To increase the likelihood of domestic tourists choosing Phung Xa lotus silk village, the following strategies can be implemented to enhance its appeal as a cultural tourism destination with experiential offerings:

- Highlight the village’s traditional and unique values: Marketing efforts should concentrate on the village's distinctive cultural features, including the lotus silk production process, historical narratives, and the artistic

merits of its products. This will foster positive perceptions among tourists and encourage visits to Phung Xa.

- Enhance the village’s appeal through multimedia: Utilize videos, images, and testimonials to create a compelling and positive image of the craft village. This can help increase awareness and interest among tourists, thereby promoting the intention to choose the destination. Increase online visibility through social media, websites, and digital content to attract a wider audience. Use digital content such as articles, images, videos, and customer reviews to create a positive impression. Encourage tourists to share their experiences and feedback through online platforms. These methods not only help improve the services but also build trust with other potential tourists.

- Offer cultural experiential activities: To enhance the visitor experience, it is necessary to create interactive activities that allow tourists to directly engage with artisans and local people. Tourists should be encouraged to participate in activities such as silk-making, attending silk weaving classes, combining these experiences with the other local festivals. These activities not only help tourists foster a deep understanding of local culture but also create personal connections, which lead to memorable experiences, increased interest, and the greater likelihood of return visits.

- Renew and update tourism programs: Develop diverse tour packages centered around the lotus season or local culture events to cater to different interests, hence boosting tourist engagement.

- Improve accessibility and service convenience: Improve access to the village by providing more information on directions, offering shuttle services from major points in Hanoi, and taking advantage of the new tourism route: “*Discovering the Nam Thang Long Heritage Trail*” launched by Hanoi Department of Tourism in April 2024 to promote tourism and attract tourists. This helps tourists feel more comfortable and convenient when visiting, thereby increasing perceived behavioral control (PBC). Additionally, ensuring that

accompanying tourism services such as dining, community accommodation, and other amenities are of good quality not only improves the tourist experience but also facilitates their planning of visits.

Conclusion

The trend of cultural tourism linked with experiences is becoming increasingly popular and attracting more tourist interests. Drawing on the Theory of Planned Behavior, the research paper 'IC' investigates the intention to select Phung Xa Silk Village as a cultural tourism destination. The study focuses on the influence of the following factors: Travel motivation (TM); Destination information (DI); Attitude (AT); Subjective norm (SN); Perceived behavioral control (PBC). The results show that three factors that have an impact on the intention to choose a cultural tourism destination linked to experiences at Phung Xa silk village are Attitude, Perceived behavioral control, and Travel motivation. The factors Destination information (DI) and Subjective norm (SN) are not statistically significant enough to conclude their influence on the dependent variable 'Intention to choose Phung Xa lotus silk village as a cultural travel destination associated with experiential activities'. The discussions and proposed solutions in the article focus on improving tourists' attitudes towards the destination, enhancing perceived behavioral control, and better meeting tourists' travel motivations. These efforts will contribute to increasing the intention and commitment of domestic tourists to choose Phung Xa silk village as a cultural tourism destination associated with experiences. As mentioned in the problem statement, this study delves into the factors influencing the decision to choose experiential cultural tourism destinations. The impact of individual characteristics like gender, profession, age, and hometown on tourists' behavioral intentions remains underexplored. Furthermore, the study's scope is currently limited to domestic tourists in Hanoi at a specific point in time. Consequently, future research could explore these relationships further by conducting mean

difference testing and expanding the sample population. The findings could be generalized to other craft villages both domestically and internationally, particularly those with distinctive cultural elements and products.

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